

Sacred Echoes References to 'Bheri Vadya' in Vaishnava Agama

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ABSTRACT:

Ancient musical instruments hold a significant place in human history and cultural heritage. These instruments created during the ancient period offer unique insights into the musical traditions, artistic expressions, and social contexts of the past and help us explore the details of their construction and the cultural significance they hold in various rituals. 'Vaishnava Agama' refers to the set of rituals, principles, and practices followed in Vaishnava traditions, which are centered around the worship of Lord Vishnu or his various avatars. The primary musical instruments commonly used in Vaishnava Agama rituals include the mridangam, kartalas (hand cymbals), gongs, conch shells, and various types of drums such as Bheri, Pataham, etc. 'Bheri' is an ancient musical instrument mentioned in various Sanskrit and other literature. According to Agama Sastra, this is one of the 'Pancha Maha Vadyas', references to which are found in the lyrics of a few musical compositions too. The Sound of Bheri Vadyam is loud, deep and creates a rhythmic and vibrant atmosphere. The mention of this instrument in Vaishnava Agamas such as Pancharatra and Vaikhanasa is not limited to the description of its usage during various rituals, festivals and invocations of deities, but also describes about the way of worshipping the instrument and the qualities that a player of 'Bheri' should possess.

However, it is disheartening to note that this instrument, which is used in various forms as a folk instrument and an instrument used in Agama traditions, is falling into oblivion today. Over the years, the Bheri Vadyam has become less common, and its usage has decreased. However, efforts are being made to preserve and promote this traditional instrument and there is much more that needs to be done so that the traditional, cultural and musical significance of 'Bheri Vadyam' is passed on to posterity.

This paper is a theoretical exploratory research on the 'Bheri' Vadyam as used in the Agamic texts and is an attempt to study and preserve the music and musicological knowledge of the instrument to bridge the gap between ancient and modern musical traditions, for an enriching appreciation of our musical heritage. This humble attempt, offers a glimpse into the music, rituals, and social fabric of the past, highlighting the need for an interdisciplinary nature of research in this field, involving archaeologists, musicologists, historians, and anthropologists.

Keywords: Bheri, Vaishnava Agama, Musical Instrument, Pancha Maha Vadyas, Avanaddha Vadya

Introduction

The Agamas encompass various aspects of Temple planning and construction, image creation, idol installation, Temple worship, and Temple festivals. In Sanskrit literature, the term "Agamas" is used in different contexts. The word "Agama" is derived from the root 'gam' with the preposition 'aang'. This root implies "to go," which can also be interpreted as moving mentally towards an object to be attained. In this sense, the word conveys a similar meaning to the term 'Veda'. Moreover, since the preposition 'aang' gives the root a sense of motion in the opposite direction, the term 'Agama' can also signify the transmission of knowledge from a teacher to a pupil, thus representing traditional

(Sampradaya) knowledge. Consequently, the word 'Agama' can be understood as representing the principles and knowledge upheld by the Agamas.

These Agamas are of three types: Vaishnavagama, Shiavagama, and Saktyagama. Vaishnavagama can be further classified into two types: Vaikshanasa Agama and Pancharatra Agama.

Vaishnavism that prescribes the procedures for consecrating the idols in the temples and also the day to day ritualistic forms of worship to be performed in these temples. It lays down the rituals and procedures of worship not only through mantras but also through Music.

The process involves the usage of various musical instruments, Ragas, Talas, and Nritis, as specified in the Agama Shastra. Among these musical instruments, the Bheri holds significant prominence.

Etymological understanding of the Musical Instrument Bheri

bibhyati śatravō'syā iti bhērī |

Meaning – one that frightens enemies

Bheri as Tumultuous Sound :

Bharta's Natya Sashttra it is said that

bhērīpataha bhambhābhīstathā dundubhīṇḍīṇḍīmāiḥ |

śāithilyādāyatattvācca svarē gāmbhīryamiṣyatē ||

Playing of Bheri, Pataha, and Bhambha as well as Dundubhi and Dundimas, one desires the depth of sound from their slackness and extensive surface.

Bhagavatgeetha

tataḥ śāṅkhāśca bhēryāśca paṇavānakagōmukhāḥ |

sahasāvābhyahanyanta sa śabdastumulō'bhavat ||

During the Kurukshetra war also the conch-shells, drums, tabors, trumpets, and cow-horns were sounded; that sound was tumultuous.

Hatayoga Pradipika

ādaujaladhi-jīmūta-bherī-jharjhara-sambhavāḥ |

madhye mardala-śāṅkhotthā ghaṇṭā-kāhalajāstathā ||

In the text Hatayoga Pradipika of Swatmarama there is mention of Bheri as it's tumultuous sound.

Chaitanya Bhagavatam

A Bengali text by Bhupathi Dasa also mentions Bheri

hari-dhvani kolahala mrdanga-kahala sankha, bheri, jayadhaka bajaye visala

There was a tumultuous vibration of the chanting of the Lord's holy names mixed with the sounds of Mridanagam, Conchshells, Kahala and Bheri.

Bheri – As Avanaddha Vadya

sēllukā jhallarī bhāṇastrivalī dundubhistathā |

bhērīniḥsāṇa tumbakyō bhēdāḥ syuravanaddhagāḥ ||

In Saranagdeva's Sangita Ratnakara given - Selluka , Jhallari, Bhaana, Trivali , Dundubhi , Bheri , Nissana and Tumbakya, all come under the category of Avanaddha vadyas.

One interesting note that According to Cf. Prof. Bhandarkar's "Jaina Iconography" Mentioned Bheri as trumpet that is Sushira Vadya while explaining pancha maha sabdas.

Lakshana of Bheri

vitastitrayadairdhyā syād bhērī tāmreṇa nirmitā |
 caturviṃśatyāṅgulē ca vadanē valayānvitē ||
 tasyāḥ savalayē carmacchannē chidrasamanvitē |
 rajjvā niyantritē gāḍhaṃ madhyē sūtrēṇa bandhanam ||
 dakṣiṇasthēna kōṇēna vāmahastēna tāḍanāt |
 udbhaṭō bhavati dhvānō gambhīrō'ribhayaṃkaraḥ ||
 taṃkāraḥ pāṭavarṇō'syāṃ mukhyō niḥśaṅkakīrtitaḥ |
 iti bhērīlakṣaṇam

Sangita Ratnakara says the construction and lakshna of Bheri as follows.

Face of the instrument - Circle (24 inches), Height of the instrument should be 3 Vitasthis i.e 36 inches. (one Vitasthi = 12 Inches)

Bheri is made of copper. The skin covering the face should have holes around it and ropes should be tied tightly in the center through the holes. If you strike the right hand with the left hand, a terrible sound should be heard.

Review of letitarure**Skandapurana:**

śaṅkhabhērīnināḍaiśca paṭahānāṃ ca nisvanaiḥ |
 vīṇāvēṇumṛdaṅgaiśca jhallarīsvaramaṅgalaiḥ ||4||

Skandapuramam Reva khanda given - During the Abhishekotsava of Senapur Chakrateertha the instruments Shanka, Bheri ,Pataha ,Venu,Veena,Mridanga and Jhallari were played.

Shiva puranam :

tadā dundubhayō nēdurbhērītūryāṇyanēkaśaḥ |
 vīṇāvēṇumṛdaṅgāni tathā gandharvaniḥ svanāḥ ||

At that point of time (when Lord Indra made Kumara(Kartikeya) to mount over the elephant Airavata during the war between Kumara and Tarakasura), the war drums,kettle drums, bheris , turyas , lutes , flutes and cymbals were sounded while Gandharvas sang the war songs.

tatō bhērīmṛdaṅgāśca paṭahānakagōmukhāḥ |
 vinēdurvihata vīraiḥ śrīṇvatām subhayānakāḥ ||

That great warriors sounded the military band and drums, besides playing on the kettle drums, cymbals, patakas, ankusas and gomukhas etc.

Agni puranam :

abhiṣiktaḥ śivaṃ viṣṇuṃ pūjayēdbhāskarādikān |
 śaṅkhabhēryayādinirghāṣaiḥ snāpayēt pañcagavyakē ||

The god said- The initiated disciple duly installed in the soul region, should worship the god Vishnu, the Sun and other gods, with the peals of Bheri, Shanka and other instruments. (A man who bathes the gods with the composition known as Panchagavya, carries with him into the region of bliss, the souls of all his departed manes and progenies.)

vēśyā śrīrṭō nṛpaḥ kanyā gaurddantī murajadhvajau |
 śrīrājyadadhiśaṅkhāmbu chatraṃ bhērī phalaṃ surāḥ || 38 ||

A Courtesan , A King, A Virgin, A Cow, An Elephant, A Flute , A Banner, as well as pots of curd, thickened milk or clarified butter, A conch shell (Shankha) , an umbrella, a vessel of water, a Bheri , A fruit , rice , gold and silver should be deemed as auspicious sights if seen in front in the course of his journey.

sujaptaśaṅkhabhēryyādinisvanaśravaṇēna vā |
saṁdahatyēva saṁyuktō bhūtējōvyatyayāt sthitaḥ || 19 ||

Even the sound of Bheri or Shanka consecrated with the present Vyatya mantra, would rouse a patient out of a state of apparent death (due to snake bite) , through the energy of the Bhu Bija mantra contained in the mighty Vyati.

Linga puranam :

bhērīmrdaṅgakādyaiśca paṇavānakagōmukhaiḥ |
vāditairvividhaiścānyaiḥ paṭahairēkapuṣkariḥ ||

(Lord Ganesha has come to the sabha of Lord Shiva) playing the instruments Bheri, Mridanga, Panava, Aanaka, Gomuka, Pataha and Ekapushkara.

jharjhariḥ śaṅkhaṭahairbhērīdīṇḍima gōmukhaiḥ |
lalitāvasitōdgītairvṛttavalgitagarjitaiḥ ||

(During the pooja of Lord Shiva the Siddhas, devas, gandharvas, Brahma and others such as Upendra) use the instruments- Jharjhari, Shankha, Pataha, Bheri, Dindima and Gomukha and sing in Low medium and high pitches.

Garga Samhitha

bherī-mṛdaṅgairbahu-dundubhi-svanaiḥ
su-gāyakairvandi-janaiścāmāgadhaiḥ
vārāṅganā-nṛtya-manojña-bhāvair
jayety abhūn maṅgala-śabda uccakaiḥ

While king Nanda's procession was going on the Musical instruments like Bheri, Mridanga, Dundhubhi, Veena and Venu were played.

Varaha Purana : The Importance of Bheri Vadya in the worship of Lord Vishnu

śrīvarāha uvāca:

bhērīśabdamaḥṛtvā tu yastu māṃ pratibōdhayēt |
badhirō jāyatē bhūmi ēkajanma na saṁśayaḥ ||
tasya vakṣyāmi suśrōṇi prāyaścittam mama priyam |
kilbiṣād yēna mucyēta bhērītāḍanamōhitaḥ ||
yasya kasyacinmāsasya śuklapakṣē tu dvādaśīm |
ākāśāsayanam kṛtvā śīghram mucyēta kilbiṣāt ||
ya ētēna vidhānēna vasudhē karma kārayēt |
aparādham na gacchēta mama lōkāya gacchati ||

|| bhērītāḍanāparādhaprāyaścittam ||

Lord Varaha says to Bhudevi - O Bhumi (Bhudevi) ! Whoever wakes me up without playing Bheri will be deaf for one lifetime. O Sushroni! Let me tell you my favorite atonement for this guilt. By this one can be freed from the sin of not playing Bheri.

One who sleeps outside on Shuklapaksha Dwadashi in any month will be freed from this sin. O Vasudha! Whoever performs Bhagavatarkarma in this way becomes free from guilt and attains my world.

References of Bheri in Vaishnava Agama

Pancharatra Agama :

Let us now examine some of the references to the musical instrument Bheri mentioned in the various processes of worshipping God, construction of temples as prescribed by Pancharatra Agama Shastra.

Garbhanyasa Vidhi: In the process of constructing the Garbhalaya temple, a copper plate is planted in the ground at night time only. It is mentioned in the Paadma Samhita that on this occasion, instruments like Shankha and **Bheri** are played aloud.

References of Bheri in Different Devatahvanam :

Agni : There is a mention about Bheri while invoking Agni
*lōkahitānugatāhuti pāvaka havyakulādhipatim
 havānamēkamajam parayāgatayā varadam
 jñānasamādhi kṛtākhilavandita kāraṇamē tadvāyusakham
 bhēri sumardala paṭahasu ghōṣaṇa pāvaka tālamidam
 tattat pāvaka tālamidam*

Nairuthi : There is a mention about Bheri while invoking Nairuthi
*aññānarūpa mahānaravāhana khadgadharmaṃ ca vibhum
 kuṃcita kēśa guṇānvita bhūṣaṇa ghōṣakulā kulitam
 vandita daitya kulākulitākhila cāmara brndayutam
 bhēri sumardala paṭaha sughōṣaṇa nirurṭi tālamidam
 tattat nirurṭi tālamidam*

Vayavya : There is a mention about Bheri while invoking Vayavya
*viśvasṛṣṭi layasthiti prabhujīvitam prabhujīvitam
 vyōmadēśa vimāna citkala niṣkalaṃ mṛgavāhanam
 dēvadānava mānuṣādi pipīlikādiha jīvanam |
 vātātādita bhēri ghōṣaṇa vāyutāla midam priyam
 tattat vāyutāla midam priyam*

Isanya : There is a mention about Bheri while invoking Isanya
*naṭanadaruhita paṭahatrīkṛta bhērikānana ghōṣaṇam |
 vṛṣabha galaghana ghaṭita ghaṇaghaṇa ghaṇṭa ghōṣa vighaṭṭanam |
 sakala suravara vihita dhamaruka ḍambarāya nayānugam |
 sakala suravara vijaya śubhakaramīśatālamidam priyam ||
 paśvīśatālamidam priyam //*

Also mentioned the method of Bheri Tadana and worshipping the Instrument

Vaikhanasa Agama :

Let us now examine some of the references to the musical instrument Bheri mentioned in the various processes of worshipping God as given by Vaikhanasa Agama Shastra.

As per Sri Vaikhanasa Bhagavatsatrokta Brahmotsvanu Kramanika following text the method of ritualistic worship of Bheri vadya explained.

“autsavam dēvam dhvajārōhaṇamaṅtapē saṃsthāpyālaṅkṛtya dviguṇārādhanam kṛtvā puṇyāham vācayitvā , prāñānāyamyā dēśakālausaṃkṛtya, asya dēva dēvasya , mahōtsavē, dhvajārōhaṇakarmamṅgam bhērīpūjām kariṣyē (itisamkalpya) āgnēyyām dhānyapīṭhē bhērīmsamsthāpya śucīvōhavyā, agnīśucī ritiprōkṣya "ōṃ śucīvōhavyā” “agnīśucivratata maśucī

rvipra śsuci:kavi:l śucī rōcata āhutaḥ| udagnē śucayastavaśukrā bhrājastāiratē, tava jyōtīgṃ śyarcayaḥ||" tasyām, ōṃbhūtēśa māvāhayāmi, ōṃ mahābhūta māvāhayāmi, ōṃ viṣṇubhakta māvāhayāmi, ōṃ gadādhara māvāhayāmi, itibhūtēśam (carmaṇi) prajāpatim (sūtrē) śēśam (dakṣiṇōttarayō:) sūryacandrau (dakṣiṇasuśirē) saptamā tṛḥ (vāmasuśirē) bhūmim (valayē) vṛṣabham (tadbandhē) indram (daṇḍē) vācaspatim (vādakē) samdīśamcāvāhya, bhūtēśādi bhēryadhi dēvēbhyaṇamaḥ āsana pādyācamana puṣpagandha dhūpadīpa havi:pānīya tāmbūla praṇāmā ityēkādaśōpacārān samarpayāmi. agnim pariśēcyā ōṃ bhūtēśāya svāhā, mahābhūtāya svāhā, viṣṇu bhaktāya svāhā, gadādhārāya svāhā, prajāpatayē svāhā, śēśāya svāhā, sūryāya svāhā, candramasē svāhā, saptamātr̥bhya svāhā, bhūmyai svāhā, vṛṣabhāyassvāhā, indrāya svāhā, vācaspatayē svāhā, samdīśāyasvāhā, vyāhṛtyam vaiṣṇanam hutvā2stampariśēkaṃ kuryāt. atō dēvāḥ ||bhūssvāhā || adi tē2svamaggamsthāḥ.”

The Utsava Murties are to be brought into the Dwajarahana mantapa and then the Alankaram, Aaradhanam is to be done. After that Punyahvachanam, Pranayama are to be done and the Mahasankalpam, wherein the name of the diety and the name of the Utsava are mentioned, is to be recited. With this the first step of Dhvajarahana, Bheri pooja starts.

In the Aagneya (South-West) direction of the mantapa, the Bheri is to be placed in a Dhaanyapeetham and Prokshana is to be done with the recital of Veda Mantras. Aavahana of deities like Bhutesha, Mahabhoota, Vishnubhakta, Gadadhara is to be done into the Bheri.

Avahana of –

Prajapathis is into the Sutras of the Bheri.

Sesha is into the Dakshina (South) and Uttara (North) sides of the Bheri.

Surya and **Chandra** is into the Dakshina Sushira.

Saptamatrukas is into the Vama Sushira.

Bhoomi is into the Valayam.

Vrushabha is into the Bandhanam.

Indra is into the Danda (Sticks).

Nandeeshwara and **Vaachaspati** into the Vadaka (Player of the Bheri).

After the Aavahana, Aasana, Arghya, Paadya, Achamana, Pushpa, Gandha, Dhoopa, Deepa, Havana, Paaneeya, Tambula is to be given to the deities, the Bheri and the player of the Bheri and Pranayama and 11 Upacharas are to be done.

Then in the Aagneya Direction, ie South-West direction, a Sthandila (A place to do Havana) is to be prepared and a Shad-Vaishnava Homam is to be done.

Bheri Tadanam and Lakshna of Vadaka:

“paścā cchuddhōdaka snāninam śuddhavastrō ttarīyōrdhvapuṇḍra śikhāya jñōpavīta pavitradhāriṇam śuddhada stanakham nirāhāram jitēmdriyam. pāraśavam tam vādakamāhūya vastrādyairalaṅkrītya ācāryaḥ prāṅgmukha udānmakhōvā bhūtvāprāṇānāyamyā, asyadēvadēvasya ..svāmīna:.... mahōtsavē, dhvajārōhana karmāṅgam bhērītādānam kariṣyē (itisaṅkalpya) upāśvāsaya iti dundubhisūktam japtvā, “upāśvāsayaḥprīthivī mutadyām purutrā tēmanutām viṣṭhitamjagat | sadum̐dubhēsajūindrēṇa dēvairdūrā ddavīyō apasētha śatrūn! ākrandaya balamōjōna ādhāniṣṭanihi dūritābādhamānaḥ | apaprōthadundubhē ducchunāgam itaindrasya muṣṭirasi vīḍayasva, āmūraja pratyāvarta yēmāḥ kētu maddundubhirvāpadīti, samaśvaparnāścara nīnōnarō2smaka mindrarathinō jayantu ||” dakṣiṇaka rēṇa yaṣṭimprānavē nādāya “ōṃ” bhūrbhuvassuvariti vadan trissantāḍayēt. “bhūḥ, bhuvāḥ, svavāḥ” paścā dindrāya vācamiti vadan, “ōṃindrāya vācam vadatēndram vājamjāpayatēndrōvā jama jayat ||” vādakēna sarvavādya samāyuktaṃ bhērīm tāḍayēt.”

Vadaka-Lakshnam: After the Agni Samskaram, the vadaka should do the Mangalasanam, wear clean and white clothes (Suddha vastram), Uttareeyam, Urdhva-Pundram, Sikha, Yagnopaveetam, and Darbhavastram. He should have clean Nails and clean and neatly aligned Teeth. He should not eat

anything until the Devatahvanam is done. He should be able to conquer his Indriyas and he should be skilled in the Bheri tadanam or the playing of Bheri. This kind of a Vadaka is to be selected and Avahanam is to be done for him. Then, Alankaram is to be done to him with Vastram.

Then, the Yagnyacharya, either facing East or North, should perform Pranayama and recite the Sankalpam which indicates the commencement of Bheri Tadanam.

Then the yagnyacharya, reciting veda mantras, asks the instrumentalists to play the instruments. Then with his right hand he takes the sticks by reciting the pranava and then strikes the Bheri 3 times reciting pranava and Bhu:, Bhuva:, Suva: . Then, Aahvanam of various deities is done starting with Devata-Adhipati Indra. While doing the Aahvanam of Indra, the Gadya or Talam of Indra is sung and all the instruments along with Bheri are played.

Likewise all the deities are invited with the recital and performance of their respected gadya, talam, vadyam and nrittam.

References of Bheri in Deferent Devatahvanam :

Indra Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Indra during Ankurarpana.

*aṇḍamaṇḍala khaṇḍavibhrama viśapakṣaja vainajam
tālakāhala tāla bhēdana bhērikānuga ghōṣaṇam
gaṇḍamaṇḍala kuṇḍaliśvara viśakuṇḍala maṇḍanam
aṇḍadōdara bandhabandhura kuṇḍarōragabhūṣaṇam
gaṇḍamaṇḍala caṇḍitāhava **bhērikāhala** ḍammbaram
śankhaśṛṅga mṛdaṅga saṅgama garuḍatāla midam mahat*

Sri Rama Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Sri Rama during Ankurarpana.

*amaragaṇahita paramapadamuni yajñaniṣkṛti rakṣaṇam
sakalasuragaṇa samayaparibhava vairirāvaṇa hiṃsakam
nikhilaniścara ditijanirasana nāśa**bhērika** tāḍanam
paṭahatuṭinaṭa caṭanakṛtiraghu rāmatāla midam harē :*

Sri Krishna Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Sri Krishna during Ankurarpana.

*narakamuramukha sakalasurariṇi nāśa**bhērika** tāḍanam
nikhila munijana niyamayamamukha bhēdikamsa susaṃhṛtam
avatūtatapaṭa nibīḍaraṇagata tāratābhīnayā nugaṃ
trijagadanugata muraliravakṛta kṛṣṇatāla midam harē:*

Brahma Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Brahma during Ankurarpana.

*aṇḍamaṇḍala kōṭimaṇḍita nābhi paṃkaja viṣṭaram
aṇḍapiṇḍa carācarāsura dēvarākṣasa sṛgvibhum |
kaṃsavairi padābjatatpara cittayukta caturmukham
bhēritāḍana ḍambarākṛti brahmatāla midam mahat ||*

Agni Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Agni during Ankurarpana.

*lōkahitānu gatāhuti vāhaka havyakavya kulādhipatiṃ
vāhanamēkamajaṃ paramaṃ parayā dayayā varadam
jñānasamādhi kyatānugatākhila kāraṇa mētaḍvāyu sakham
bhērikatāḍana tālavibhēdana pāvakatāla midam*

Yama Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Yama during Ankurarpana.

*kāladūtapati kālamēghanabha kālapāsadhara kālavit
kālacakrākṛti kālacakrapati kālakāraṇa mahattanum
kālakētusakha kālahāripada kālapūjyaka rasapriyaṃ
bhērikānugata tālabhēdayama tālamēta diyacōditam*

Varuna Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Varuna during Ankurarpana.

*sakalakalpavikalpa kāraṇa pralayakalpa lasattanum
udadhijatprabhu divyamakarasa vāhapāśa bhṛtamparam
jaladhisapta samṛddhiprajaladhi vikramarṣa samṛddhidam
garuḍasannidhi bhēritādāna varuṇatāla midam mahat*

Vayu Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Vayu during Ankurarpana.

*viśvasṛṣṭi layasthiti priyajīvitam prabhujīvitam
vyōmadēśa vikāravitkala niṣkalaṃ mṛgavāhanam
dēvadānava mānuṣādi pipīlikāvadhā jīvakṛt
pādatālana bhēritādāna vāyutāla midam mahat*

Kubera Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Kubera during Ankurarpana.

*śāṅkhanidhi padmanidhi vanditadhanēśam kālakula nāsasakha dēvakula dīpaṃ
śyāmala tanurmanīkirīṭa makuṭāṅgaṃ vuṣpakarathapriya kaṃpriya nidhīśam
brahmapada viṣṇupada rudrapadacittam vāsavapada prada dhanaprada nidhīśam
bhērimukha rēcakavivūri maṅghōṣam śambhusakha kumbhaka kubērahita tālam*

Isanya Gadyam

There is a mention of Bheri in the invocation of Isanya during Ankurarpana.

*naṭanapadahita paṭahajhaṭikṛta bhērikānuga ghoṣaṇam
vṛṣabhagalagata ghaṭitamañirava ghaṇṭaghoṣa vighaṭṭakam |
ditiya niśacara nihitadamuruga ḍambarājita yānugaṃ
sakalaturagaṇa vijayaśubhakara mīśatāla midammahat ||*

There is a lot of references of Bheri in deferent rituals according to Vaikhanasa Agama.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study of ancient musical instruments such as the 'Bheri Vadyam' holds immense significance in understanding cultural heritage and musical traditions. The 'Vaishnava Agama' rituals, centered around the worship of Lord Vishnu, have been an essential part of the musical landscape, with the 'Bheri' being one of the primary instruments used in these traditions.

Despite its historical importance, it is disheartening to witness the 'Bheri Vadyam' falling into oblivion today. The decrease in its usage poses a threat to the preservation of this traditional instrument and its cultural significance. However, efforts are underway to protect and promote the 'Bheri Vadyam,' ensuring that its musical heritage is passed on to future generations.

This research paper serves as a valuable contribution to the preservation and study of the 'Bheri Vadyam' within the context of Agamic texts.

In conclusion, the exploration of ancient musical instruments like the 'Bheri Vadyam' not only allows us to cherish our cultural roots but also encourages us to preserve and cherish these precious pieces of history for a harmonious future, where the echoes of the past can resonate with the generations to come.

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Interviews

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2. Interview with Dr PTG Ranga Ramanujacharyulu, Asst.Professor, Department of Agama, National Sanskrit University, Tirupati.